

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS IN MATHEMATICS IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION: IDENTIFYING THE CHALLENGES IN THE MUNICIPAL NETWORK OF SANTA INÊS, BAHIA, BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article presents a comprehensive analysis of the results of an evaluation conducted across the entire municipal education network of Santa Inês, in the state of Bahia, covering students from the 2nd to the 9th grade. The article focuses on the mathematics tests and uses statistical analyses, particularly the internal consistency criteria Cronbach's Alpha, along with the reference matrix of the Basic Education Assessment System (SAEB, acronym in Portuguese). The main objective of this research is to understand the current reality of student performance in mathematics in the municipal network of Santa Inês. To achieve this objective, the data collected in the evaluation are subjected

the results, providing valuable insights into how the students of Santa Inês-BA compare with national standards and which specific areas of mathematics may require greater attention. The results of this analysis will serve as the basis for the formulation of educational public policies in the municipality, aiming at improving the teaching of mathematics and, consequently, increasing student performance. The research has a significant impact on the allocation of resources and efforts to areas of greatest need, contributing to the quality of education in Santa Inês-BA and to informed decision-making in the field of education. This study highlights the importance of statistical analysis and the use of tools such as Cronbach's Alpha and the SAEB reference matrix to understand the local educational landscape, as well as to support evidence-based educational interventions.

RESUMO

Este artigo científico apresenta uma análise abrangente dos resultados de uma avaliação realizada em toda a rede municipal de ensino de Santa Inês, no estado da Bahia, abrangendo alunos do 2º ao 9º ano. O artigo trata do recorte nas provas de matemática e utiliza análises estatísticas, em particular os critérios de consistência interna Alfa de Cronbach, juntamente com a matriz de referência do Sistema de Avaliação da Educação Básica (SAEB). O objetivo principal desta pesquisa é compreender a realidade atual do desempenho dos alunos em matemática na rede municipal de Santa Inês. Para atingir esse objetivo, os dados coletados na avaliação são submetidos a análises estatísticas rigorosas, incluindo o cálculo do Alfa de Cronbach para avaliar a consistência interna das provas. A utilização da matriz de referência do SAEB permite uma análise comparativa e contextualizada dos resultados, fornecendo insights valiosos sobre como os alunos de Santa Inês-BA se comparam com os padrões nacionais e quais áreas específicas da

consequentemente, ao aumento do desempenho dos alunos. A pesquisa tem um impacto significativo no direcionamento de recursos e esforços para áreas de maior necessidade, contribuindo para a qualidade da educação em Santa Inês –BA e para a tomada de decisões informadas no campo da educação. Este estudo destaca a importância da análise estatística e da utilização de ferramentas como o Alfa de Cronbach e a matriz de referência do SAEB para compreender o panorama educacional local, bem como para embasar intervenções educacionais com base em evidências.

INTRODUCTION

Santa Inês is a municipality located in the state of Bahia, in the Northeast of Brazil. Founded in 1962, the municipality has unique geographical and socioeconomic characteristics. With regard to educational data from elementary education, they play a crucial role in the development of the local community. Santa Inês-BA has a municipal education network that serves elementary school students. This network is responsible for providing a solid educational foundation for the children of the region. Like many municipalities in Brazil, Santa Inês faces challenges in the educational system, including the need to improve learning rates in Mathematics, Portuguese, and other elementary school subjects.

The analysis of student performance in elementary education is essential to understand educational progress. This involves applying assessments and tests to identify areas of difficulty and implement improvement strategies. This study consists of a statistical analysis of the results of evaluations carried out in the network (Santa Inês Educational Assessment System – SAESI) by all students enrolled from the 2nd to the 9th grade in the municipal network of Santa Inês-BA.

results of the Basic Education Assessment System (SAEB, acronym in Portuguese) test of the municipality itself, the state of Bahia, and Brazil, in order to understand the current panorama and future perspectives of performance in SAEB.

THE IMPORTANCE OF CONDUCTING AN ASSESSMENT IN THE NETWORK TO DEVELOP WORK STRATEGIES

Conducting assessments in the education network, whether student performance evaluations, curriculum assessments, or institutional evaluations, is essential for the development and improvement of education quality. These assessments provide valuable information that helps to develop more effective work strategies and drive educational progress.

Assessments allow for the identification of the specific needs of students, teachers, and schools. Based on the results, it is possible to direct resources and efforts to areas that require more attention, such as subjects in which students face more difficulties. Continuous evaluation of student performance provides data that makes it possible to track their progress over time, which is crucial to ensure that all students are advancing in their academic skills according to established educational goals. Additionally, assessment results enable educational managers and teachers to make informed decisions about the curriculum, teaching methods, resource allocation, and intervention programs, all aimed at maximizing student learning.

Assessments also help identify gaps in the curriculum and areas that can be improved, allowing schools to adjust their study programs to meet the specific needs of students and ensure that the curriculum is relevant and aligned with educational standards. Accountability and transparency are

educators can use assessment results to identify areas where they need to improve their pedagogical practices, promoting continuous professional development and the improvement of teaching.

Sharing assessment results with parents and community members can create a sense of shared responsibility for educational success, involving stakeholders in discussions on how to improve local education. Finally, assessments can serve as a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of educational policies at the municipal, state, or national level, helping in the formulation of more grounded and effective policies.

ANALYZING THE DATA

The SAESI Assessment was conducted between May and September 2023 in the five schools of the municipal network of Santa Inês, Bahia, Brazil, involving about 900 students from the 2nd to the 9th grade of Elementary School II. In this article, we will evaluate the specific results from the 6th to the 9th grade in the subject of Mathematics, but we will also use data obtained from the analysis of the previous school years.

Taking Freire (1970) as a reference, he advocates for formative assessment, which is continuous and oriented towards learning. He supported the idea of assessments that help students reflect on their own learning and progress.

Peregrino (2005) addresses the challenges and importance of educational assessment in the 21st century, highlighting the role of exams as an essential tool in collecting data to improve teaching and learning. He discusses how exams can provide valuable information for educators, researchers, and decision-makers, helping to guide curriculum development, identify areas for improvement, and monitor student

In Table 01, we present the performance data by school year for the Santa Inês-BA Education System in the Assessment Applied to Elementary School II students.

Table 01. General results of the municipality.

Stage	Indicator	Number of students	SAESI 2023.2 (% = points)	IDEB Municipal Average 2021- Mathematics	IDEB 2021 Average
6th grade Elementary School	Mathematics	118	38.21% 191.05 points	—	—
7th grade Elementary School	Mathematics	104	38.30% 191.5 points	—	—
8th grade Elementary School	Mathematics	126	32.24% 161.2 points	—	—
9th grade Elementary School	Mathematics	112	38.32% 191.6 points	222.87	4.4

Source: Authors (2024).

Source: Authors.

To better understand the information contained in the above table, we chose to clarify the captions:

- What is the SAESI average? It is the average for the referenced school year, considering ALL students in the indicated school year.
- What is the Municipality SAESI average? It is the average of all students evaluated through the SAESI assessment, considering ALL (445 students) students in the school network who took the assessment.
- What is IDEB? It is an important metric used to assess the quality of basic education in Brazil. It is calculated based on various factors that reflect students' performance in national assessments, as well as the school approval rate.

The column with SAESI-SAEB data refers to the score achieved in the SAESI test converted to SAEB parameters, considering a full flow (1.00)

of attention that will be discussed later in our text. Table 02 presents the performance standards of students in Mathematics for each school year.

Table 02. Performance standards per school year.

Grade	Below Basic (less than 20%)	Basic (from 20% to 50%)	Adequate (between 50% and 74%)	Advanced (equal to or greater than 75%)	Students in levels Below Basic and Basic	Students in levels Below Basic and Basic (%)
6th	17	86	15	0	103	87.29%
7th	21	66	17	0	87	83.65%
8th	28	95	2	1	123	97.62%
9th	18	83	8	3	101	90.18%

Source: Authors (2024).

Fig 02. Number of students per year school concerning their performance standards. A) In absolute values. B) In a percentage base.

Source: Authors (2024).

TEST RELIABILITY

Reliability is the probability of an item performing its function for a specified period under defined conditions of use. Cronbach (1951) defined the alpha coefficient as a measure of the internal consistency of a test or scale. This measure is widely used in evaluating the reliability of measurement instruments, whether they are questionnaires, psychometric tests, or rating scales.

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, where values closer to 1 indicate greater internal consistency, meaning that the test items are consistently correlated. Therefore, when assessing the reliability of a test, Cronbach's alpha coefficient is a widely accepted reference measure,

He demonstrated how this measure can be used to evaluate the consistency of test items and how it can be interpreted in research data analysis. Since then, Cronbach's alpha coefficient has become an essential tool in assessing the reliability of measurement instruments in various research areas, including psychology, education, medicine, and other social sciences. Therefore, by using Cronbach's alpha coefficient in this research, we are following a widely recognized and established practice in evaluating the consistency and reliability of tests and scales.

The confidence interval of the test based on Cronbach's alpha coefficient is given by: Poor (0.00 – 0.69), Fair (0.70 – 0.79), Good (0.80 – 0.89) and Excellent (0.90 – 0.99). Considering the universe of analysis, we have the following test reliability results in Table 06.

Table 03. Compiled data on the reliability of the applied test.

School year	Number of students	Cronbach's alpha		Reliability
6th grade	118	Mathematics	0.61	Poor
7th grade	104	Mathematics	0.68	Poor
8th grade	126	Mathematics	0.42	Poor
9th grade	112	Mathematics	0.69	Poor

Source: Authors (2024).

research phase.

ANALYSIS OF CONSIDERED MOST DIFFICULT AND EASIEST QUESTIONS

The evaluation consisted of 20 multiple-choice questions in the area of mathematics, each with 4 alternatives — one correct and three distractors — covering various topics, descriptors, and proficiency levels. The analysis is based on the number of correct and incorrect answers to the questions presented to students in the SAESI Assessment, according to the reference matrix.

Table 04. Most difficult questions 6th grade.

Code	Descriptor	Correct Questions
D25	Carry out calculations involving operations with rational numbers (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	9.32%
D26	Solve problems with rational numbers that involve operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	11.02%

D21	Recognize the different representations of a rational number.	13.56%
D17	Identify the location of rational numbers on the number line.	24.58%
D28	Solve a problem involving percentages.	26.27%
D21	Recognize the different representations of a rational number.	27.12%
D28	Solve a problem involving percentages.	27.12%
D19	Solve problems with natural numbers involving different meanings of operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	28.81%
D19	Solve problems with natural numbers	31.36%

	subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	
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Source: Authors (2024).

Table 05. Easiest questions 6th year.

Code	Descriptor	Correct Questions
D21	Recognize the different representations of a rational number.	80.51%
D36	Solve problems involving information presented in tables and/or graphs	72.88%
D26	Solve problems with rational numbers that involve operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	72.88%
D26	Solve problems with rational numbers that involve operations	69.49%

	potentiation).	
D23	Identify equivalent fractions.	61.02%
D19	Solve problems with natural numbers involving different meanings of operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	55.93%
D17	Identify the location of rational numbers on the number line.	52.54%
D28	Solve a problem involving percentages.	40.68%
D24	Recognize the decimal representations of rational numbers as an extension of the decimal numbering system, identifying the existence of "orders" such as	34.75%

D26	Solve problems with rational numbers involving operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	33.90%
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Source: Authors (2024).

Table 06. Most difficult questions 7th grade.

Code	Descriptor	Correct Questions
D28	Solve a problem involving percentages.	13.46%
D17	Identify the location of rational numbers on the number line.	17.31%
D33	Identify an equation or a first-degree inequality that expresses a problem.	19.23%
D25	Carry out calculations involving operations with rational numbers (addition, subtraction, multiplication,	22.12%

D33	Identify an equation or a first-degree inequality that expresses a problem.	25.96%
D34	Identify a system of first-degree equations that expresses a problem.	26.92%
D25	Carry out calculations involving operations with rational numbers (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	26.92%
D24	Recognize the decimal representations of rational numbers as an extension of the decimal numbering system, identifying the existence of "orders" such as tenths, hundredths and thousandths.	30.77%
D34	Identify a system of first-degree equations	32.69%

D26	Solve problems with rational numbers involving operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	33.65%
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Source: Authors (2024).

Table 07. Easiest questions 7th year.

Code	Descriptor	Correct Questions
D36	Solve problems involving information presented in tables and/or graphs.	57.69%
D19	Solve problems with natural numbers involving different meanings of operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	57.69%
D19	Solve problems with natural numbers involving different	57.69%

	multiplication, division and potentiation).	
D16	Identify the location of whole numbers on the number line.	54.81%
D36	Solve problems involving information presented in tables and/or graphs	52.88%
D16	Identify the location of whole numbers on the number line.	50.96%
D17	Identify the location of rational numbers on the number line.	50.00%
D29	Solve problems involving proportional, direct or inverse variations between quantities.	50.00%
D26	Solve problems with rational numbers that involve operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication,	47.12%

D24	Recognize the decimal representations of rational numbers as an extension of the decimal number system, identifying the existence of “orders” such as tenths, hundredths and thousandths	39.42%
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Source: Authors (2024).

Table 08. Most difficult questions 8th grade.

Code	Descriptor	Correct Questions
D13	Solve problems involving the calculation of the area of plane figures.	7.14%
D26	Solve problems with rational numbers that involve operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and exponentiation).	11.90%

	On the number line.	
D28	Solve problems that involve percentage.	17.46%
D21	Recognize the different representations of a rational number.	18.25%
D24	Recognize the decimal representations of rational numbers as an extension of the decimal numbering system, identifying the existence of “orders” such as tenths, hundredths, and thousandths.	24.60%
D5	Recognize the conservation or modification of measures of sides, perimeter, and area in the enlargement and/or reduction of polygonal figures using grid meshes.	24.60%
D30	Calculate the numerical value of an	27.78%

D33	or a first-degree inequality that expresses a problem.	28.57%
D3	Identify properties of triangles by comparing measures of sides and angles.	30.16%

Source: Authors (2024).

Table 09. Easiest questions 8th year.

Code	Descriptor	Correct Questions
D12	Solve problems involving calculating the perimeter of plane figures.	71.43%
D19	Solve problems with natural numbers involving different meanings of operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	57.94%
D3	Identify properties of triangles by	45.24%

D37	Associate information presented in lists and/or simple tables with the graphics that represent them and vice versa	45.24%
D18	Perform calculations with integers involving operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	44.44%
D34	Identify a system of first-degree equations that expresses a problem.	41.27%
D20	Solve problems with integers involving operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	34.92%
D6	Recognize angles such as changes in direction or turns, identifying right and non-right angles.	34.13%

	variations between quantities.	33.33%
D4	Identify relationship between quadrilaterals, through its properties.	33.33%

Source: Authors (2024).

Figure 03. Percentage of the easiest and most difficult questions answered correctly by school year. A) 6th grade. B) 7th grade. C) 8th grade.

Source: Authors (2024).

FEATURED INDICATORS

guarantee the right to learning. The following tables present, by area and by school year the highlighted indicators.

Table 10. Most accurate skills/descriptors in Mathematics.

Year	Descriptors – Most Accurate Skills/Descriptors in Mathematics	Descriptors – Least Correct Skills/ Descriptors in Mathematics
6th grade	D21 – Recognize the different representations of a rational number.	D25 – Carry out calculations involving operations with rational numbers (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).
7th grade	D36 – Solve problem involving information presented in tables and/or graphs	D28 – Solve a problem involving percentages
8th grade	D12 – Solve a problem involving calculating the perimeter of flat figures.	D13 – Solve a problem involving calculating the area of flat figures.
9th grade	D1- Locate explicit information in a text.	D21- Recognize different positions between two or more opinions relating to

Here we see a limitation regarding RESOLVING, as a critical point in Mathematics, which points to the urgent need to intervene with diverse activities that help in the development of these skills, highlighting the fact that this item was the most critical in the application of the test SAESI in the initial grades.

RESUMPTION OF SEQUENTIAL DATA

Below we present in summary the descriptors highlighted for each school year. This global vision helps us visualize the education network as a whole.

Table 11. Highlighted descriptors in Mathematics and average proficiency by school year.

School year	Best Developed Descriptor	Descriptor with Limitations	Perc.	Proficiency Average	Level
2nd	D1 – Associate a number of objects in a collection with a	D7 – Decompose natural numbers.	54.86%	274.3	Proficient - Level 6

3rd	D8 – Calculate the result of addition or subtraction involving natural numbers.	D29 – Solve problems using the decimal writing of banknotes and coins of the Brazilian Monetary System.	40.09%	200.45	Basic – Level 4
4th	D22 – Identify the time on digital or pointer clocks.	D12 – Solve a problem that involves more than one operation with natural numbers.	45.99%	229.95	Proficient – Level 5
5th	D28 – Read information presented in bar or	D13 – Recognize and use characteristics of the	50.43%	252.15	Proficient - Level 6

		such as groupings and exchanges in base 10 and the principle of place value.			
6th	D21 – Recognize the different representations of a rational number.	D25 – Carry out calculations involving operations with rational numbers (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation).	38.21%	191.05	Basic – Level 3

7th	involving information presented in tables and/or graphs	Solve a problem involving percentages.	38.30%	191.5	Basic – Level 3
8th	D12 – Solve a problem involving calculating the perimeter of flat figures.	D13 – Solve a problem involving calculating the area of flat figures.	32.24%	161.2	Insufficient – Level 2
9th	D1 – Locate explicit information in a text.	D21 – Recognize different positions between two or more opinions relating to the same fact, or	38.32%	191.6	Basic - Level 3

Fig. 04. Students' score in mathematics from 2nd to 9th grades.

Source: Authors (2024).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The analysis of the presented skill descriptors reveals the existence of descriptors that demonstrate a solid development in students' competencies, while others show limitations. In the group of better-developed descriptors, we can highlight the ability to associate a quantity of objects with natural numbers, calculate additions and subtractions involving natural numbers, identify times on digital or analog clocks, read information on bar or column graphs, and locate explicit information in a text.

On the other hand, the descriptors with limitations indicate areas where students may encounter challenges. These include the decomposition of natural numbers, solving problems involving more than one operation

percentages, calculating perimeter and area of flat figures, as well as recognizing different positions among various opinions related to the same fact or theme.

Therefore, the conclusion of this study indicates that educational efforts need to be directed toward strengthening the competencies related to the descriptors with limitations. This can be achieved through more effective teaching strategies, improved educational resources, and a more comprehensive curriculum approach that addresses the identified challenge areas in greater depth. Additionally, it is important to recognize the significance of curriculum adaptation and attention to the individual needs of students to ensure that everyone has the opportunity to fully develop their skills in mathematics and reading.

Ultimately, the evaluation of the descriptors provides valuable information that can guide the improvement of teaching and learning, ensuring that students acquire the necessary skills to face the challenges of today's world. Building a solid foundation in these areas is essential for the educational and intellectual development of students, preparing them for a future of success and achievements.

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